

Does the Rules of Physics Vary Overtime? – 8T on Dirac Idea

O Manor

June 30, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the two main equations of the 8T, the varying Lorentz manifold yielding a negative time invariant acceleration from it and the primordial coupling constants series, it is than possible to provide a take on Dirac idea regarding the laws of physics changing with the epos.

Introduction

Equations (1) to (1.131) describe main two rules we have in the 8T. The main equation describes (1) a varying Lorentz manifold, which proved to experience arbitrary variations to vanish into matter. This equation also describe negative time invariant flow acceleration from extremum curvatures on the manifold, i.e. "dark energy", in addition to describing Einstein principle of equivalence.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad - \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \quad (1.11)$$

The second main equation is the primordial coupling constants series, which proved bosons to be net curvature on the manifold. The bosonic fields are isomorphic to prime numbers or one, as given by (1.3). Bosonic fields are ripples on the matric tensor. Such ripples are curvature vortexes as can be represented by spin as in equation (1.33):

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1 \quad (1.33)$$

Now that our framework is set up, only two equations we have dark energy, fermions bosons, general relativity and all within one framework and no infinities of any sort. Analysis of the Dirac idea can be represented. Are the laws varying? According to the 8T framework, the laws are the same. The acceleration at singularity are no different from the acceleration today, 13.7B years later. What is different is the state of the manifold. It is more flat and much colder. Each manifold is flattened by other manifolds that are wrapped around it, all the manifolds taken to be stationary. The multiverse is a packet of universes structure all described by variation of equation (1). If the prime ring is isomorphic to itself on each manifold, than the coupling constants series (1.31) is also invariant, the bosons are the same.

The difference and here is the key to this short essay is that each manifold has different likeability to experience different bosonic propagations according to its age. The meaning is that if the manifold is young, the coupling constants are at the beginning of the series, the strong interactions is dominating, as time goes by, fermion clusters are created and the series experience infinitely weaker bosonic fields. The older the manifold, the weaker the interactions are getting. Any civilization not familiar with this series will conclude each universe to be different since it has different bosons, but a civilization familiar with this series knows that it's a function of time and all bosons are figures of the same hand. All are curvature on the matric tensor, generated by the same element, from the second and above. The rules are the same, the stages are different. By analyzing those two equations, we can reach a wonderful simplifications regarding the invariance of the rules under shifting universes and state – Dirac was wrong. If the laws were different at each stage of the universe, there could not be GR and QM which has not varied since their publication over a hundred years ago for example of GR. Varying overtime does not necessarily means billions of years, we can examine this claim in short periods and examine whether the laws are varying or not.

Assuming the laws are varying at each point, that means that nature will generate new set of laws to each segment of time, which is not Lagrangian oriented. In fact it is the inverse of the Lagrangian oriented. If our entire framework of QFT is revolved around minimizing the action, it is reasonable to assume that nature minimize the laws governing it. In our 8-theory, the only law is (1) and to assume new set of laws for each temporal segment does not seem quite as reasonable option for a final theory of physics. To sum up, the stages are different, but laws are time and manifold invariant.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor "The Coupling Constants Series – Spin" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor "The Coupling Constants Series – Electrons" In: (2021)
- [4] O. Manor "Photon Emission – The Coupling constant series" In: (2021)
- [5] O. Manor "Bosonic Propagations and Cyclic Groups"" In: (2021)
- [6] O. Manor "Curvature Vortexes" In: (2021)